

1 **Any contribution of the season change to the spread**
2 **of COVID-19 caused by SARS-CoV-2?**

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16 **Abstract**

17 **Background:** Most people raise a similar concern during this tough time of the
18 COVID-19 pandemic caused by SARS-CoV-2 infection regarding when this outbreak
19 will come to end. A recent thorough-general study on the success of China dealing
20 with COVID-19 outbreak has concluded to recommend the need for a multi-sectoral
21 approach to prevent future outbreaks of emerging infectious diseases including for the
22 still-occurring COVID-19 outbreak with the initiative for the highest interest of the
23 health of mankind

24 **Main text:** The prevalence of SARS-CoV as the predecessor of SARS-CoV-2 has
25 been concluded to be more suitable in spring than autumn and winter, with nothing
26 prevalency in summer. No coincidence that SARS-CoV-2 infection has outbreak
27 around the world from January 2020 to the present, April 2020, as ever predicted to
28 reoccur based on its predecessor, SARS-CoV, that have prevalence been high since
29 January, February, March, April, until early May 2003. As opposed to other seasons,
30 summer has low atmospheric pressure as its exemption that provenly causes virus
31 inactivation.

32 **Conclusions:** The denotative nature of SARS-CoV-2 seems to reflect its predecessor,
33 SARS-CoV, which begins nearing the end of the year and reaches its optimum hence
34 in spring, thereafter, finally ends in summer. Low atmospheric pressure in the summer
35 impresses that it is the potential cause of ending the outbreak by deactivating SARS-
36 CoV-2, apart from the hot temperature of weather. The knowledge to be gained here
37 is further closely correlated to the fact that coronavirus is able to have genetic
38 recombination that may bring about new genotypes and, consequently, outbreaks later
39 occurring.

40 **Keywords:** COVID-19, outbreak, pandemic, SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2, season,
41 atmospheric pressure, hot temperature.

42

43 **Introduction**

44 Most people raise a similar concern during this tough time of the COVID-19
45 pandemic caused by SARS-CoV-2 infection regarding when this outbreak will come
46 to end. The awaited theme of a study but yet may still need more time to further
47 investigate. Recently, a thorough-general study by Qian et. al. on the success of China
48 dealing with COVID-19 outbreak has concluded to recommend the need for a multi-

49 sectoral approach to prevent future outbreaks of emerging infectious diseases
50 including for the still-occurring COVID-19 outbreak with the initiative for the highest
51 interest of the health of mankind [1]. Of the scarcity of studies on this theme, the
52 association between the season factors and the spread of outbreak starts raising to be
53 anticipated, which has not been mentioned and emphasized by Qian et. al. on their
54 analysis toward the systematic approach that protecting the planetary health from the
55 infectious diseases causing the outbreak as in COVID-19 pandemic.

56 **Main text**

57 There is an enigma yet to clearly define for the role of the weather temperature in the
58 occurring of the outbreak [2], such as SARS-CoV-2 causing COVID-19 infection,
59 that still questionable. Whilst history repeats itself to present inspiration; motivation;
60 solution; and prediction, the prevalence of SARS-CoV as the predecessor of SARS-
61 CoV-2 has been concluded to be more suitable in spring than autumn and winter [2],
62 with nothing prevalency in summer. Something that has been surprisingly indicated
63 from hundred years ago regarding when ending of something outbreak [3] and it is no
64 coincidence that SARS-CoV-2 infection has outbreak around the world from January
65 2020 to the present, April 2020 [4], as ever predicted to reoccur based on its
66 predecessor, SARS-CoV, that has prevalence been high since January, February,
67 March, April, until early May 2003 [2]. The timing of the onset of SARS-CoV-2
68 infection in December 2019 [4] appears to be patterned with the emergence of its
69 predecessor, SARS-CoV, in November 2002, which is associated with the optimal
70 range of environmental temperatures for SARS-CoV between 16°C to 28°C from
71 November to April [2]. Nonetheless, in the current case of SARS-CoV-2 infection,
72 many countries that have lower or even higher temperatures cannot avoid
73 experiencing this COVID-19 outbreak [4]. Contrary even further to much-arguable

74 common presumptions that an outbreak will difficult to existence on the hot
75 temperature of the weather, escalating a crucial question, to our notion, that what
76 factor solely summer can make the difference compared to other seasons so no
77 prevalence for SARS-CoV and hence probably as also for SARS-CoV-2, if not due to
78 hot temperature. Apparently, as opposed to other seasons, summer has low
79 atmospheric pressure as its exemption [5] that provenly causes virus inactivation [6]
80 including, in our view, as probably ever occurred to SARS-CoV and later-predictable
81 be happened to SARS-CoV-2 when entering summer. Supporting a well-established
82 concept that can be said to be similar, in our opinion, that even the best management
83 of patients with SARS-CoV infection or SARS-CoV-2 is to be treated in isolation
84 rooms with negative pressure. The cold atmospheric pressure has even been echoed to
85 be a part of an effective disinfection method and environmentally-friendly for space
86 and water disinfection [6].

87 **Conclusions**

88 The nature of SARS-CoV-2 indicatively appeared to be mirroring of its predecessor,
89 SARS-CoV, that begun at near to the end of the year and reaching its optimum later in
90 spring, then, eventually ended in summer. The research to be undertaken by the
91 scientific community on this scarce theme may benefit more by focusing on the role
92 of low atmospheric pressure in summer that may suggest becoming the cause of the
93 ending of the outbreak by inactivating SARS-CoV-2, irrespective to the hot
94 temperature of weather. The knowledge to be gained here is further closely correlated
95 to the fact that coronavirus able to have genetic recombination [7], which may bring
96 about new genotypes and, consequently, outbreaks later occurring. Therefore, dealing
97 with the possibility of re-emergence of SARS-CoV-2 and other new viruses need for
98 more comprehensive preparedness.

100 **List of abbreviations**

101 COVID-19: Coronavirus disease 2019

102 SARS-CoV: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus

103 SARS-CoV-2: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2

104

105 **Declarations**

106 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

107 Not applicable

108 **Consent for publication**

109 Not applicable

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111 This published article includes all data generated or analyzed during this study.

112 **Competing interests**

113 The authors declare to have no competing interests.

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116 **Author's contributions**

117 FZA and MKS contributed equally to this work. FZA conceptualized the study;

118 analyzed and interpreted all data, and was a major contributor in writing the

119 manuscript. MKS conceptualized the study; analyzed and interpreted all data, and was

120 a major contributor in critically revised the manuscript. ZA inspired the study and

121 critically revised the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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